

ULOGATA NA DEFEKTOLOGOT VO DEFEKTOLOJ KATA DI JAGNOSTI KA

Lidija BAJLOZOVA

Sojuz na def ektol ozi na
Rapubl i ka Makedoni ja

Rezi me

Vo ova izlagawe e istaknata ulogata na def ektologot vo def ektolo{ kata di jagnostika, kako bitna komponenta od celokupnata rehabilitacija na licata so pre~ki vo razvojt. Ulogata na def ektologot vo def ektolo{ kata di jagnostika e mo{ ne kompleksna i zna~ajna za ponatamo{ nata rehabilitacija. Poleto za rabota na def ektologot vo def ektolo{ kata di jagnostika navistina e golemo, a so toa e golem i negoviot pri dones vo spre~uvawe ili namaluvawe na brojot na licata so pre~ki vo psihofizi~kiot razvoj. Def ektologot go zabele`uva odnesuvaweto i mo`nosti te na licata vo socijal noto pole.

Voved

^ovekot kako bi opsi hosocijal na cel i na somatski, mentalni i op{ testveni komponenti, koi se me|usebno zavisni i obusloveni od ra|aweto i niz celiot `ivot e izlo`en na razni vlijani ja. Seto toa se odrazuva najrazli~no vrz negovata celokupna li~nost. Naru{ uvaweto na integritetot na li~nosta doveduva do naruf uvawe na bi opsi hosocijalni ot entitet, koe bara ti mska rabota od stru~waci od razni prof ili: lekari, psihol ozi, def ektol ozi, socijalni rabotnici, rabotni instrukt ori.

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THE ROLE OF SPECIAL TEACHER IN SPECIAL EDUCATION AND REHABILITATION DIAGNOSIS

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Abstract

This presentation indicates the role of special teacher in Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis, as an important component of the complete rehabilitation of people with disabilities. The role of special teacher in Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis is very complex and important for further research. The special teachers' activities in Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis cover large area, so their contribution towards preventing of decreasing the number of people with disabilities is great. The special teachers note people's behavior and possibilities in the social field.

Introduction

Human beings, as a bio-psycho-social unity of somatic, mental and social components, mutually dependant and conditioned, since birth and throughout the entire life have been under different kinds of influences which are reflected on their personalities. The impaired integrity of the personality brings impairments to bio-psycho-social entity that requires team and professional work of different profiles: doctors, psychologists, special teachers, social workers and instructors.

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Rehabilitacija kako predmet na defektologijata ima karakter na integralen pristap. Integralnata rehabilitacija ja soinuvaat kliničkiot, edukativniot i socijalno-ekonomski ot del.

Kliničkiot del na rehabilitacijata vidno zaostanuva vo sporedba so edukativni ot del. Nedosti got na organizirana i so zakon sankcionirana celosna praktika-koja vo sebe bi sodr`ela preventiva, detekcija, dijagnostika i tretman-go onevozm`uvaat razvitokot i izgradbata na nau-no zasnovaniot i op{testveno opravdani ot sistem za rehabilitacija na hendikepiranite.

Defektolo{kata rabota vo odnos na medicinskata, kako specifičnost, vo sebe sodr`i i preventivna aktivnost. Spored toa, kliničkiot del sodr`i: preventiva, detekcija, prijavuvawe i evidencija, dijagnostika, prognoza i tretman. Defektologot, kako len na eden polivalenten tim, so dijagnostički postapki i stru-na osposobenost vo edukativniot i rehabilitativniot proces, dava ogromen pri dones vo otkrivawe gol embroj hereditarni (nasledni), kongenitalni (vrodeni) ili rano steknati pri~ini kako i vo spreuvawe na ostavaweto posledici vrz razvojot na li~nosta. Vo ova moe izlagawe sakam da go potenciram znaeweto i ulogata na defektologot vo procesot na defektolo{kata dijagnostika kako komponenta na kliničkata defektologija, koja ima neprocenljivo znaewe za uspehot na celokupnata rehabilitacija. Navremenata detekcija i pravilnata dijagnostika ovozmo`uvaat da se odstranat ili da se ubla`ati da se dovedat vo tolerantno nivo site pre~ki vo razvitokot, za da mo`e da se postigne maksimalnoto mo`no nivo na razvoj na sposobnosti te kaj li~nosta. Ottuka bi proizleglo deka kliničkiot del na rehabilitacijata vidno zaostanuva vo sporedba so edukativni ot del. Nedosti got od organizirana i so zakon sankcionirana celosna praktika-koja vo sebe bi sodr`ela preventiva, detekcija, dijagnostika i tretman-go onevozm`uvaat razvitokot i izgradbata na nau-no zasnovaniot i op{testveno opravdani ot sistem za rehabilitacija na hendikepiranite. (2, 3)

Rehabilitation as a subject of Special Education has a character of integral approach. Integral rehabilitation is consisted of clinical, educational and socio-economic part.

The clinical part of rehabilitation remarkably lags behind the educational part. The lack of organized, as well as sanctioned by law practice – which would implement prevention, detection, diagnosis and treatment – disables the development of scientifically based and socially justified system of rehabilitation of people with disabilities.

Special Education and Rehabilitation work compared with medical one as a specific, consists in itself preventive activities. According to that, the clinical part consists of prevention, detection, report and evidence, diagnosis, prognosis and treatment. The special teacher, as a member of one polyvalent team, with diagnostic procedures and professional training in the education and rehabilitation process, gives enormous contribution to discovering a great number of hereditary, congenital or early gained reasons, as well as prevention of consequences on the personality's development. I would like to emphasize the role of the special teacher in the process of Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis as a component of clinical Special Education and Rehabilitation that has priceless importance for the whole rehabilitation success. The prompt detection and right diagnosis enable to remove and moderate or to bring to level of tolerance all developmental disabilities in order to achieve maximum developmental level of the personality's abilities. This shows that the clinical part of rehabilitation lags behind the educational part.

The lack of organized, as well as sanctioned by law practice – which would implement prevention, detection, diagnosis and treatment – disables the development of scientifically based and socially justified system of rehabilitation of people with disabilities. (2, 3)

Met odologija za rabota

PREDMET NA I STRA@UVAWETO

Ulogata na defektologot vo defektolo{ -kata di jagnostika.

CELI NA I STRA@UVAWETO

Da se vidi ulogata na defektologot vo primenata na op{ tata defektolo{ ka di jagnostika kaj decata so pre~ki vo razvojt.

Da se vidi uspe{ nosta na navremenata i pravilna defektolo{ ka di jagnoza.

HI POTEZI

Hi pot eza 1-Se pretpostavuva deka op{ tata defektolo{ ka di jagnostika treba da bide instrument za rabota na defektologot vo procesot na edukacijata i rehabilitacijata na licata so pre~ki vo razvojt.

*Hi pot eza 2*Se pretpostavuva deka so primenata na di jagnosti~kite testovi defektologot treba da ja procenuva: dominantnata lateraliziranost, organiziranosta na psihomotorikata, prakti~kata, gnosti~kata i praktognosti~kata organiziranost, govorot i komunikacijata, soznajnite funkcii i povedenieto na deteto vo odnos na kalendarskata i mentalnata voznost, so cel prezemawe reedukacija na psihomotorikata, za uspe{ na socializacija i integracija vo sredinata.

Hi pot eza 3-Se pretpostavuva deka defektologot e va`en ~len vo multidisciplinarnite timovi, vo zdravstvenite slu`bi i vo masovnite vospitno-obrazovni ustanovi.

Ulogata na defektologot vo di jagnosti~kata postapka

Defektologot so primena na op{ tata defektolo{ ka di jagnostika e vo mo`nost da izvri dopolnuvawe na opisot na licata na deteto od aspekt od koj ne se vo mo`nost toa da go storat ni medicinskata i psiholo{ kata di jagnostika.

Methodology of work

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

The role of the special teacher in Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis

RESEARCH GOALS

The research goals are to investigate the role of the special teacher in implementation of general Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis of children with developmental disabilities.

Furthermore, its goal is to investigate the prompt and right Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis.

HYPOTHESES

Hypothesis 1 – It is assumed that general Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis has to be a working tool for the special teacher in the process of education and rehabilitation of people with developmental disabilities.

Hypothesis 2 – It is assumed that with implementation of diagnostic tests, the special teacher has to estimate: dominant lateralization, organization of psycho-motor, practical, Gnostic and practical-Gnostic organization, speech and communication, knowledge functions and children behavior according to calendar and mental age, with aim to take the reeducation of psycho-motor for successful environmental socialization and integration.

Hypothesis 3 – It is assumed that the special teacher is an important member of multidisciplinary team in health services and mass institutions for education.

The role of special teacher in diagnostic procedure

The special teacher, with the change of general Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis, is able to supplement the description of child's personality from the aspect that is not possible to be described by medical and psychological diagnosis.

Defektologot, koj se zanimava so defektološka dijagnostika, stoji pred edno golomo področje na aktivnosti. Kako dijagnostička metoda koristi anamneza, opazovanja in ocena.

Naodi te na defektologot se sporeduvajo naodi te na lekarot in psihologot. I taka, preko eden multidisciplinaren pristop, ovie naodi dobivajo polna vrednost. Defektologot vo dijagnostikata se zanimava so funkcije na ličnost v odnos na postopke na ličnost v socialno pole vo prostor in vreneto.

Dijagnostički pristop vo defektologijata voopstoma da go podelimo na opstotno primenuva sekoj defektolog, brez razlika na potesnoto strukturno usvajanje specifičnih to se upotrebuje specifično v odnos na prirodata na hendikep, so koj se zanimava defektolog-specialist.

Od ličnosti na ispitivač-defektologot, in od negovata organiziranost vo rabetata zavisi kako je se izvede celata dijagnostička postopka.

Dijagnostička postopka, vsučnost po-nuva so zemawe anamnestički podatoci. Pri zemaweto anamnestički podatoci se trgnuva od pretpostavki koi subjektot gi objasnuva na način na koj toj znae, a ne od teoriski pretpostavki. Anamnestički podatoci se zabeleuvaat na način to e avtentičen na način na ni vnoto opič uvawe od sogovornikot. Dokolku toj e preopstren, defektologot mo da go reži mirno negovoto izlagawe, no pri toa dobro e sekoga da se navede ponekoja rečenica to go karakterizira na način na izlagawe ili koja plastično go prikauva opič uvaweto na pojavata od sogovornikot.

Celiot tekst na anamnezata mora da bi denapič an taka da mu ovozmoži na sekoj sleden ispitivač sami ot da si donese zaključok vrz osnova na suroviot materijal, iznesen vo anamnezata. Seto toa treba da se opič onaka kako to go opič uva ispitani kot. Duri na kraj defektologot dava svoj sud, t.e. defektološki zaključok. Anamnestička postopka pretpostavuva zemawe podatoci za problemi te koi deteto, ili vozas-

The special teacher, who is not involved in Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis, is faced with a huge area of activities. The special teacher uses anamnesis, observation and estimation as a diagnostic method.

The special teacher's findings are compared with those of doctors and psychologists. Thus, through a multidisciplinary approach these findings gain their value. The special teacher in the diagnosis deals with the functions of personality in relation to the personality's existence in the social field in space and time.

The diagnostic approach in Special Education and Rehabilitation is usually divided in general – applied by each special teacher regardless their professional specialization – and specific – used specifically in relation to the nature of disabilities, matter of work of specialists.

The entire diagnostic procedure depends on the examiners – the special teachers and their work organization.

The diagnostic procedure starts with anamnesis data. While taking the anamnesis data, the special teachers start from assumptions explained by subjects in the way they know and not from theoretical assumptions. The anamnesis data are noted in authentic way they are received by the one who gives them. If the diagnostic data are too extensive, the special teacher can summarize it, quoting from time to time sentences that can characterize the way of expressing and truly presenting the appearance by the one who gives them.

The entire text of the anamnesis has to be written in the way which will enable every other examiner to bring own conclusion from the raw material, presented in the anamnesis. The whole anamnesis has to be presented truly. At the very end, the special teacher gives the Special Education and Rehabilitation conclusion. The anamnesis procedure is recording the problems the child or the adult mani-

nata li~nost, gi manifestira i poradi { to do|a da bara pomo{ od def ktologot. Podatocite mo`e da se zemaat od subjektot poedine~no od negovite roditeli ili od ~lenovite na potesnoto semejstvo, kako i od drugi li~nosti { to se vo kontakt so ispitanikot. Anamnesti~kite podatoci mo`e da se nadopolnat so socijalna anketa, koja se pravi vo semejstvoto, u~ili { teto, rabotnoto mesto ili vo druga sredina vo koja prestojuva ispitanikot. Anamnesti~kite podatoci { to gi dava sami ot ispitanik se narekuvaat **avt oananneza**, dodeka podatocite { to gi davaat negovite roditeli ili nekoj drug se narekuvaat **het eroananneza**. Anamnezata se zema so vospostavuvawe neposreden fizi~ki kontakt me|u ispituva~ot i ispitanikot.

Opservacite se od izvonredno zna~ewe za defektologot. Tie imaat golemo zna~ewe vo defektolo{ kata di jagnostika. Opservacijata nekoga{ po~nuva u{ te vo vedni del na dijagnosti~kata postapka, u{ te vo hodni kot pri ~ekaweto, pri vleguvaweto v kancelarija. Pri toa se zabel e` uva negovoto odnesuvawe kon roditelite i obratno, odnosot na roditelite kon deteto, kako i odnosot na deteto kon defektologot kako ispituva~. Pri nabquduvaweto defektologot go zadr` uva vni mani eto vrz mi mi~nata muskulatura, nasmevkata, dr`eweto na teloto, odot i gesti kulacijata. Deteto vo kontakt so defektologot mo`e da manifestira tri vi da povedeni e:

- pregolem strav, priti snatost do roditelite, odbiva razgovor so defektologot;
- deteto vleguva vo sobata so pregolema qubopitnost i razdvi`enost so { to ja ote`nuva rabotata na defektologot;
- deteto stapuva vo razgovor so defektologot so lesna napnatost, koja postepeno popu{ta.

Opservacijata, kako stru~no izvedena dijagnosti~ka postapka, go dava premi not od subjekti vnoto do`i vuvawe na deteto od defektologot kon objekti vi zi rawe na negovite kvaliteti i negovite problemi .

fest and ask help from the special teacher. The data can be taken from the subject individually – from parents or next of kin, as well as other people close to the examined person. The anamnesis data can be supplemented with social questionnaire conducted in the family, school, working post or any other environment the examined person stay. The anamnesis data given by the examined person are called *auto-anamnesis*, while data given by the parents or other people are called *hetero-anamnesis*. The anamnesis is taken with making direct physical contact between the examiner and the examined.

The observations are of extraordinary importance for the special teacher, as well as for the Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis. Sometimes the observation starts even in the introductory part of the diagnostic procedure, in the waiting room or while entering the office. That records the subject's behavior towards the parents and vice versa, the parents' relations towards the child as well as the child's relation towards the special teacher as an examiner. During the observation, the special teacher pays attention on mimicry muscles, smile, body posture, walk and gesticulations. The child, in contact with the special teacher, can manifest three kinds of behavior:

- a great fear, standing close to the parents, refuses to talk to the special teacher;
- the child enters the room with great curiosity and movements which make the work of special teacher difficult;
- the child starts talking to the special teacher with easy tension that gradually declines.

The observation as professionally performed diagnostic procedure gives the pass from special teacher's subjective experience of the child to objective attitudes of qualities and problems.

Opservaci i te mo`e da bidat *sistematski* i *nesistematski*. Kaj nesistematskite opservaci i informaci i te imaat prednost vo toa { to se dobivaat vo prirodna sredi na, ovozmo`uvaat nabqduvawe i prirodno dr`ewe vo razli~ni sredi ni i vo dadeni uslovi, t.e. vo uslovi na interakcija na slu~ajot vo sredi nata. Vo takvi te slu~ai dijagnosti~arot go dijagnosti ci ra dr`eweto, karakteristiki te i li~nata interakcija za koi smeta deka se od zna~ewe. Glavni ot nedostatok na nesistematskite informaci i e ni vnata preglom subjektiva oboenost.

Kaj sistematskite opservaci i dijagnosti~arot mo`e da nabqduva edno ili pove}e dr`ewa. Toj go specif icira ili go def inira dr`eweto, a potoa ja meri frekf rencijata na traeweto, gol eminata na latencijata i va`nosta na dr`eweto. Osnovni ot nedostatok na ovoj tip opservi rawe se sostoi vo toa { to e naso~eno kon opredel ena to~ka, pri { to drugi te va`ni elementi za utvrduvawe dijagnoza mo`e da bi dat zanebareni.

Gol embroj i stra`uvawa ja poka`uvaat potrebata od pronao|awe sovremeni modeli za def ektol o{ ka dijagnostika { to }e gi opf atat si te delovi na li~nosta-biol o{ ki ot, psihol o{ ki ot i soci jal ni ot del.

I kaj decata na pomala vozrast, kako i kaj adolescentite, va`no e def ektologot da zabele`uva na koj na~in ovie deca odat, vleguvaj}i vo prostori i te kade { to se vr{ i aktivnosta; kakov im e izrazot na liceto pri toa i kakvo im e dr`eweto na teloto vo cel ina. Def ektologot go bele`i i odnosot kon zada~ite { to gi dobiva; odnosot kon drugari te so koi sorabotuva vo re{ avaweto na zada~ite; go nabqduva negovoto dr`ewe na ~asovite i odmorite, negovite ~uvstva ili psihomotornoto vladeewe vo momentite koga roditelite go doveduvaat ili go odveduvaat, i toa niz podolg peri od. Def ektologot e kadaren da go zabele`i menuvaweto na ovie vladeewa so tekot na vrameto, osi roma{ uvaweto ili z bogatuvaweto na na~i not na povedeni e, dinami kata na usvojuvawe na novite informaci i i znæwa, pa taka, na sostanokot na

The observations can be *systematic* and *non-systematic*. The advantage of non-systematic observations is that the information is acquired in natural environment, enables observation and natural behavior in different environments and in given conditions, i.e. in cases of interaction in the environment. In such cases, the diagnostician diagnoses the behavior, characteristics and personal interaction that are considered to be important. The main disadvantage of non-systematic information is its enormous subjectivity.

With systematic observations, the diagnostician can observe one or more behaviors. The diagnostician specifies or defines the behavior and measures the frequency of duration, the size of latency and the importance of behavior. The main disadvantage of this type of observation is the fact that it is directed towards certain point while other important elements for diagnosis are neglected.

A large body of research shows the need for finding contemporary models of special education and rehabilitation diagnosis that will include all parts of the personality – biological, psychological and social part.

It is very important, for both children at early age and adolescents, the special teacher to note the way of their movements while entering the premises for the activities, the expression of their faces and body posture in general. The special teachers note the assignments the child gets, the relationships with other children the child cooperates with in solving the assignments,

the feelings or psycho-motor behavior during the whole period from the moment the parents bring or take the child from the premises. The special teacher is able to note the change of behavior, its weakening or improving, dynamics of gaining new information and knowledge and at the meeting of

stru~ni ot tim e vo mo`nost da iznese eden pobogat naod za deteto vo koj se opi { uvaat negovite potencijali i mo`nosta za koristewe na tie potencijali vo socijal noto pole. Zna~i, defektologot ja nabqduva telesnosta vo akci ja-dvi`ewe. Toj anali zi - ra dali opi { ani ot kvali tet na dvi`ewe mu ovozm`uva deteto da organi zi ra akti vnos - ti vo prostorot na mani pulati vnoto pole, pravilno da go dr`i penkaloto, teloto, glavata, da go vr{ i ~i not na pi { uvawe, ili dali deteto mo`e da stoi i da tr~a vo grupa. Nieden defektolog ne mo`e kompletno da í pristapi na svojata rabota do - deka ne se inf ormi ra za toa kakva e organi - zacijata na dvi`ewata i telesnosta na de - teto vo kontekst na teloto, kako f aktor na psi hi~ki ot razvoj i socijalizacijata. De - fektologot go interesi ra dali deteto, so koe raboti, ima izedna~enost na site kva - liteti na psihomotornata organi ziranost i dali toa, na soodveten na~in, odgovara na barawata { to se javuvaat vo poletu na re - alnosta.

Opisot na li~nosta { to ja nudi defek - tolo{ kata dijagnostika ovozm`uva li~ - nosta, so kakov bi lo oblik na hendi kep, da se sogleda vo osnovni te obel e` ja na egzi - stencijal noto pole { to go gradi i vo koe `ivee. Ve}e prvata sredba vo dijagnosti ~ - kata postapka go otkri va vpe~atokot { to li ~nosta so hendi kep go ostava na drugi .

Dijagnosti ~kata postapka vo sovremenata defektologija gi koristi site pristapi { to se dadeni za preku ni v da se do`iveat i da se defi ni raat { to pogolem broj kompo - nenti, koi gi poka`uvaat poedine~nite kvaliteti na li~nosta, sekoga{ vo daden moment na nejzi noto postoeve.

Sekoja proba { to }e ja izvr{ i deteto e samo eden detal, koj zboruva za na~i not na postoeve na li~nosta deteto vo odreden realitet { to go opkru`uva. Defektologot, vr{ ej}i si ja svojata aktivnost, postoi niz na~i not na taa aktivnost { to ja organi - zira. Isto taka, toj postoi niz svojata ma - nipulati vna aktivnost - kako { to deteto, so koe raboti, postoi niz na~in na orga - ni zi rawe na svoi te akti vnosti .

professional team, the special teacher presents with many details the findings of child's potentials and abilities used in the social field. The special teacher observes the body movements in action. He analyzes whether the described quality of movements enables the child to organize activities in the space of the manipulative field, right use of pen, body and head, to write or whether the child can stand or run in the group. The special teacher cannot work without complete information about the movement organization and the child's physical abilities in the context of the body as a factor of psychic development and socialization. The special teacher is interested in whether the child has equal qualities of psycho-motor organization and whether the child responds in appropriate way to the requirements of the reality.

The description of the personality offered by the Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis enables the disabled people to be considered with all basic characteristics in the existential field that they build and they live in. The first meeting during the diagnostic procedure reveals the impression disabled people leave to the others.

The diagnostic procedure in the contemporary Special Education and Rehabilitation uses all available approaches in order to experience and define a larger number of components that show individual qualities of people, always at a certain moment of their existence.

Each rehearsal done by the child is only one detail that expresses the way of child's existence in real surrounding. The special teachers are included in the activity that they organize. They exist in their manipulative activities – as children special teachers work with exist in the way of organizing their activities.

Defektologot ne smee defektolo{ kata di-jagnostika da ja svede na izveduvawe ritualni dvi`ewa, koi nekade gi nau~il, a koi se smetaat za stru~ni.

Navisti na e te{ ko toa da se postigne, so ogle na predomi nantnosta na odredeni nau~ni disciplini i nepostoeweto ili mali~ot broj specijalizirani defektolo{ki ustanovi, osnovnata cel na defektolo{ kata diagnostika - utvrduwawe na mo`nosti te za unapreduwawe na biolo{ki ot, psiholo{ki ot i socijalni ot razvoj.

So primena na defektolo{ki te testovi defektologot pri dijagnostici raweto vr{ i procena na:

- Domi nantnata lateraliziranost i organiziranost na psihomotori kata,
- Praksi~kata organiziranost,
- Gnosti~kata organiziranost,
- Praktognosti~ka organiziranost,
- Govor i komunikacija,
- Spoznajni funkcii,
- Dr`ewe.

Defektologijata e interdisciplinarna. Taa mora da bide inicijator za organizirawe na multidisciplinarni te timovi. So ogle na toa deka sekoja diagnosti~ka postapka treba da se izvr{ i multidisciplinarno vo ramkite na timot, defektologot }e go iznese op{ti ot defektolo{ki status i statusot za specifi~nosta na defektivitetot. Op{ti ot defektolo{ki nad }e ovozm` i uvidi vo drugi te svojstva na li~nosta i slu`i za dopolnuwawe opisot na klini~kite manifestacii na ispitani kot, { to gi zabele`ale i drugi te ~lenovi na timot - psiholog, nevropsihijatar, pedijatar, socijal en rabotnik i dr.

Opisot, { to stru~ni ot tim go dobiva od defektologot, ja otkriva mo`nosta na ispitani kot vo odnos na negovite potrebi vo socijal noto pole. Dodeka zdravstveni te rabotnici gi sogleduvaat nedostatocite po struktura i funkcija, a psiholozite zboruvaat za kvalitet na neuspe{nost vo odnos na strukturi te i funkcii te, defektolozite zboruvaat za funkcii te, ne vo odnos na strukturi te, tuku vo odnos na mo`nosti te na socijal noto pole.

Special teachers must not bring down the Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis to performing ritual movements they acquired somewhere and are considered to be professional.

The main aim of Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis – setting up the possibilities for biological, psychological and social development is very difficult to achieve having in mind the predominance of certain scientific disciplines, non-existing or small number of specific Special Education and Rehabilitation institutions.

When applying Special Education and Rehabilitation tests for diagnosis, special teachers estimate the following:

- The dominant lateralization and psycho-motor organization,
- Practical organization,
- Gnostic organization,
- Practical-Gnostic organization,
- Speech and communication
- Knowledge functions,
- Behavior.

Special Education and Rehabilitation is an interdisciplinary science. It has to initiate organization of multi disciplinary teams. The special teacher will present general Special Education and Rehabilitation status and the status for specific disabilities since each diagnostic procedure should be done within the multi disciplinary team. The general Special Education and Rehabilitation finding will enable insight other people's characteristics and supplements the description of clinical manifestations of the examined people noticed by other members of the team – psychologist, neuro-psychiatrist, pediatrician, social worker and others.

The description that the professional team receives from the special teacher reveals the possibilities of the examined people for their needs in the social field. While the health workers perceive the disadvantages in structure and function, the psychologists speak about the quality of failure related to structures and functions, the special teachers talk about the functions not in relation to structures, but in relation to the possibilities in social field.

Diagnostiki i psihologot, vo vrska so strukturite i funkcijate, i diagnostikata na defektologot, vo vrska so volevata aktivnost nasovena kon drugite, se nadopolnuvaat vo celosen opis na ličnosta. (1, 4)

Zakluok

Kaj nas defektološki kata diagnostika uštetene i institucionalizirana, ne e normativno opredelena, postavena i profesionalno opredelena. Uštetija imame praktikata na klasifikacija, i toa vrz osnova na podatocite od testirawena inteligencijata, što se izveduva vo medicinske i psihološki ustanovi, koja ja sproveduvaat glavno, lekari, i psiholozi. Uštetese praktikuva kategorizacija, odnosno rasporeduvawe od stručni komisi i vrz osnova na Pravilnikot za rasporeduvawe, koi vo posledno vreme rabotat se poveševostručni ustanovi.

Najgolemi napredok vo diagnostikata, i toa voranata diagnostika, e postignat so otvorawena razvojnite sovetuvaništa. Tiese ovozmožuvaat preku evidencijate, opservacija i sledewenarizirane dekadadatarana i posigurnadiagnostika.

Segen pred mnogu godini ukažaldeka bez dobra dijagnoza nema ni dobra rehabilitacija.

Vrz osnova na postavenite hipotezi, može da gidoneseme ovi zakluoci:

- So defektološki kata diagnostika, odnosno so navremenoto dijagnostici rawe, deteto šemože navremeno da se podloži ili da se isprati na rehabilitacionen tretman i šese potvrdi tošeno negovata pošenost, što defektološki kata diagnostika e instrument za rabota na defektologot, kako **potvrda za prvata hipoteza**. Sekoj defektolog treba da go obraboti svojot i spitaniško opštadefektološki kata diagnostika.
- Defektologot šei zvrši defektološki kata diagnostika, t.e. procena na psihomotorikata so pri mena na defektološki testovi,

The diagnostic findings of the health worker and the psychologist in relation to the structures and functions and the diagnostic of special teacher in relation to the willing activity directed to others supplement each other in the complete description of the personality. (1, 4)

Conclusion

In the Republic of Macedonia, the Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis is not yet institutionalized, normatively determined, set up and professionally determined. We still practice of classification on basis of data achieved from tests for intelligence, implemented by doctors and psychologists in medical and psychological institutions. We still practice categorization, i.e. assigning professional commissions according to the Rule Book for assignments, which work in professional institutions.

The greatest progress in diagnosis, especially in early diagnosis, is achieved with opening developmental counseling offices. They enable through evidence, observation and follow up of risky children to give early and true diagnosis.

Many years ago, Seguin pointed out that without good diagnosis there was no good rehabilitation.

On the base of stated hypotheses, the following can be concluded:

- With Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis, i.e. prompt diagnosis, the child can be treated or sent for rehabilitation treatment with prompt confirmation of disability and special teacher is given an instrument for work as a proof of the **first hypothesis**. Each special teacher should apply general Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis for the patient.
- The special teacher will make Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis, i.e. estimation of the psycho-motor by applying Special Education and Rehabilitation tests which neither can be done

koja ne more da ja izvr{i ni lekarot ni tu psihologot, kako **potvrda za vtorata hi poteza**.

Niz prethodnoto izlagawe zaklu~i vme dekalinostakako zbirna fizi~ki, psihiki i socijalni sposobnosti-trpi posledici vovsite sferi i }e bide uspe{no tretirana samo so pristap na pove}e stru~waci, pri {to defektologot treba da se vklui kako ~len na stru-ni ot tim. Defektologot treba da raboti na leto na defektolo{ kata dijagnostika kako ~len na stru-ni ot tim, {to e **potvrda za tretata hi poteza**.

Predlozi

Niz diplomskata rabota se obidovme da ja pretstavime potrebata i v`nosta na rabotata na defektologot na leto na defektolo{ kata dijagnostika.

Za uspe{no vkluiuvawe i realizirawe na negovata rabota potrebno e ostvaruvawe na nekojku predlogmerki :

- Op{tata defektolo{ka dijagnostika treba da bide zastapena vov komisiite za ocena na specifi~nite potrebi na licata so pre~ki vov razvojot, kako i vov multidisziplinarnite timovi na zdravstvenite slu`bi vov masovnite vospitno-obrazovni ustanovi.
- Vov komisiite za ocena na specifi~nite potrebi na licata so pre~ki vov razvojot defektologot, pokraj specifi~nite naodi vov kontekst so defektivitetot {to dominira}e uka`e i na op{tiot rehabilitacionen potencijal na deteto. Opi{uvaj}igo vov celina i pofunkcii, kako {to e toa predvideno vov defektolo{ kata dijagnostika, defektologot ima mo`nost na drugi te ~lenovi na timot da im gi opi{e osnovnite pravci vov koi linost ostvaruva najuspe{ni kontakti so okolinata.
- Vov vospitno-obrazovnite institucii-vo koi denes se o-ekuva na stru~nite sorabotnici, pedagogi psiholog, da im se pridru`ii defektologop{tata defektolo{ka dijagnostika i masvoevidna uloga.

by doctors nor psychologists, as a **proof of the second hypothesis**.

So far, we have concluded that the personality – as a unity of physical, psychic and social abilities – faces consequences in all spheres and will be successfully treated only with an approach by more professionals and the special teacher should be included as a member of a professional team. The special teacher should work in the field of Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis as a member of a professional team, **as a proof of the third hypothesis**.

Proposals

We have tried to present the need and the importance of the special teachers' work in the field of Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis.

Several proposals-measures have to be realized for successful implementation of the work of special teachers:

- General Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis should be implemented at the commissions for assignments of the specific needs of people with developmental disabilities, as well as in multi disciplinary teams of health services, in mass education institutions.
 - At the commissions for assignments of the specific needs of people with developmental disabilities, the special teacher, besides specific findings in relation with the dominant disability, will point out the child's general rehabilitation potential.
- Describing the child in whole and in functions, according to the Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis, the special teacher presents to the other members of the team child's basic ways of making the most successful contacts with the environment.
- In educational institutions – in which the special teacher is expected to join other professional associates: pedagogue and psychologist – the general Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis has its important role.

Preku nea defektologot }e go opi { e vladeeweto na ovi e deca, onaka kako { to toj go gleda. Toj gi opi { uva kvali teti te na deteto od onaa strana na zabele`uvawe koja prethodno ja izvr{ il pedagogot. Detskoto otsustvo na vnimanie ili oblicite na dr`ewa { to ne se vkl opuvaat vo barawata na pedago{ kata rabota, def ektol ogot }e gi razlo`i na elementarni vidovi na izravawe na psihomotornata aktivnost, so { to }e go objasni i za sebe i za drugite onoj drug del na vladeeweto na deteto { to pedagogot go zabele`uva samo kako globalen ~in. Timot, { to go so~i nuvaat pedagog, psihologi def ektol og vo u~ili { tata, mo`e da gi defini ra site oblici na polesna nedogradenost na funkci i te bitni za psihosocialni ot razvoj i da gi re{ava na samoto mesto.

- Defektologot vo posebnite u~ili { ta, kako i vo drugite rehabilitacioni ustanovi, treba i neposredno da se zapoznae so li ~nosta na deteto so koe raboti, pri menuvaj}i gi metodite { to gi nudi def ektolo{ kata dijagnostika. Na toj na~in se osigurava programata za rehabilitacija, { to se bazi ra vrz toa da bide soodvetna, i spored toa i nejzini te efekti cel osni.

- Vo postojnite planovi i programi { to se primenuvaat vo u~ili { tata ne se vodi smetka za individualni te razliki me|u deca. Zatoa pri izrabotka na nastavni te planovi i programi, odgovornite stru~ni slu`bi na nadle`ni ot organ na vlasta treba da povedat smetka ova rabota da im ja doverat na def ektol ozi te.

- Osven vo koncipi raweto na nastavni te planovi i programi, def ektologot mora da vodi smetka i za metodi kata na rabota so ova populacija. Imaj}i go predvid toa deka se konkretni misliteli vo procesot na obrazovani eto, izlagaweto na def ektologot sekoga{ mora da go sledi i soodvetna konkretni zacija. Procesot na nastavata nikoga{ ne smee da se svede na ~ist verbalizam, tuku zborot na def ektologot mora sekoga{ da bide pri dru`en so soodvetno o~i gl edno nastavno sredstvo.

The special teachers through it describe the behavior of these children as they experience them. They describe the child's qualities from the pedagogue's point of view. The child's absence of attention or behavioral forms that do not fit into requirements of the pedagogical work, the special teachers will divide into elements of psycho-motor activity expression, explaining for themselves and for the others the other part of child's behavior that the pedagogue has noticed as a global act. The school team consisted of a pedagogue, psychologist and special teacher can define all forms of easy undeveloped functions that are essential for psycho-social development and solve them at the very spot.

- The special teachers in specific schools, as well in other rehabilitation institutions, have to acquaint directly the child's personality they work with, applying the methods of Special Education and Rehabilitation diagnosis. So, the program for rehabilitation is provided and is based on appropriate tendencies and their complete effects.

- The existing plans and programs that are applied in schools do not pay attention for individual differences among children. Therefore, when preparing curricula and programs, the authorized professional offices of the relevant governmental organ have to take into consideration this task to be assigned to special teachers.

- Besides outlining the curricula and programs, the special teachers have to take into consideration the methodology of work with disabled people. Having in mind that they are real thinkers in the educational process, their work requires concretization. The educational process is never considered as a pure verbalism and the special teacher's words must be accompanied by appropriate teaching aids.

• I majji predvid deka obrazovani eto na decata so pre~ki vo razvojt e speci fi ~no-zatoa { to go bara istovremeno i edukativni ot i klini ~ki pristap vo rabotata-potrebno e vo sami ot proces na nastavata, kako princip na rabota, da se obezbedi pri mena na metodata za reedukacija na psihomotorikata. Reedukacijata na psihomotorikata, { to go stimuli ra i razvojt, def ektologot treba da ja pri menuva i ndi vi dual no i nadvor od nastavni te akti vnosti .

• Considering the education of children with developmental disabilities as specific – which requires the educational and clinical approach of work at the same time – it is necessary to provide, in the educational process as a working principle, the implementation of methodology for reeducation of psycho-motor. The special teachers have to implement the psycho-motor reeducation which stimulates the development individually and out of teaching activities.

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